

Amphotis orientalis Reiche, 1861 in Bulgaria (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae)

Borislav GUÉORGUIEV

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Abstract. *Amphotis orientalis* Reiche, 1861 is recorded for the first time from Bulgaria. Short taxonomic notes, useful in the differentiation of the species from another Balkan representative of the genus – *A. marginata* (Fabricius, 1781), are added also.

Key words: Coleoptera, Nitidulidae, *Amphotis orientalis*, first record, Bulgaria

Only two species of the genus *Amphotis* Erichson, 1843, *A. marginata* (Fabricius, 1781) and *A. orientalis* Reiche, 1861, have been known in the Balkans (APFELBECK, 1916; NOVAK, 1952; JELÍNEK, 1965; AUDISIO, 1993). Interestingly, later one of these authors omitted *orientalis* in his renovated list of the beetles from the Adriatic islands of former Yugoslavia (NOVAK, 1970). IOAKIMOV (1904), ANONYMOUS (1907), and JELÍNEK (1965) reported *marginata* for Bulgaria, the latter two without exact localities.

As a result of a project funded by the Bulgarian Ministry of Education and Science, in 2002 an arachno-entomological research of the Maleshevska planina Mtn. began, a mountain area with almost unknown invertebrate fauna. One of the first more interesting finds was *Amphotis orientalis* Reiche, 1861, a new species for the Bulgarian fauna. The exact data are: south of village Tsaparevo, 550 m, 2-31.07.2002, pitfall traps in open habitat with single *Quercus* spp., 2 female specimens, S. Lazarov & T. Ljubomirov leg. The specimens are preserved in the collection of the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia. At present the known distribution of this East-Mediterranean species includes Spain (probably introduced), Italy (probably introduced), Dalmatia, SW Bulgaria, Greece, Anatolia, Syria, Lebanon, Israel, North Africa (introduced) (AUDISIO, 1993; AUDISIO et al., 1999). *A. orientalis* is rarely found in the Balkans, as three or four localities are cited from there. The genus is known as the only myrmecophile among the other nitidulid beetles in the European-Mediterranean Region (COIFFAIT, 1958). Thus, *A. marginata* is known as a permanent visitor of the nests of *Lasius fuliginosus* (Latreille) (GRZIMEK & FONTAINE, 1975). NOVAK (1952) mentioned *orientalis* under the bark of a dry trunk in an immediate proximity to *Crematogaster scutellaris* (Olivier).

Beside his faunistic contribution, APFELBECK (1916) noted also several diagnostic characters of *orientalis*, comparing it with *marginata*.

Our observations on the two specimens from Maleshevska planina could be added to Apfelbeck's comments, thus making easier the differentiation of *orientalis* from *marginata* (Table 1). The total length of the body in the two individuals studied is 5.4-5.8 mm, and their

maximum width – 2.9-3.1 mm. The antennae of both species and the apex of ovipositor of *Amphotis orientalis* are illustrated (Figs 1-3).

Figs 1-2. *Amphotis orientalis*: 1 - right half of head with antenna, dorsal view (after AUDISIO, 1993: 114, fig. 29c-d). Scale line = 0.1 mm; 2 - apex of ovipositor. Scale line = 0.25 mm

Fig. 3. *A. marginata*: right half of head with antenna, dorsal view (after AUDISIO, 1993: 114, fig. 29c-d). Scale line = 0.1 mm

Table 1

States of some external characters useful in the differentiation of *A. orientalis* from *A. marginata*

Characters	<i>A. marginata</i>	<i>A. orientalis</i>
Magnitude and shape of 1 st antennomere	Larger and transversal, auriculate	Lesser and sub-rounded
7 th and 8 th antennomeres	Almost as long as wide	Wider than long
Colour of pronotum	Sharply two-colored	One-colored (rusty yellow)
Colour of elytra	Sharply two-colored	Dimly one-colored (disc somewhat darkened)

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Author's address:

Dr. Borislav Guéorguiev
National Museum of Natural History
Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd. 1
1000 Sofia, Bulgaria
E-mail: bobivg@yahoo.com

***Amphotis orientalis* Reiche, 1861 в България (Coleoptera: Nitidulidae)**

Борислав ГЕОРГИЕВ

(Резюме)

Amphotis orientalis Reiche се съобщава за пръв път за фауната на България. Материалът е събран наг с. Цапарево в Малешевската планина, на 550 m надморска височина. Представени са кратки таксономични бележки, полезни за различаването на този източномедитерански вид от другия балкански представител на рода - *A. marginata* (Fabricius). Според типа на хабитата, *A. orientalis* може да бъде класифициран като мирмекофил. Изследването е резултат от работата по проект "Б-МУ-1101/01", финансиран от Министерството на Образованието и науката (МОН).